

THERMAL PERFORMANCE INDICATORS OF BIOGAS OBTAINED AS A RESULT OF PROCESSING ORGANIC BIOMASS

¹Botir Egamberdievich Khairiddinov, ²Sobir Achilovich Utaev

^{1,2}Karshi State University, Karshi. st. Kuchabag-17,180103

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15430201>

Biomass processing under anaerobic conditions is carried out in special, pressurized digesters (Fig. 1). Under the influence of methane-forming bacteria in an oxygen-free environment at a temperature of 30 ... 55 ° C, the biomass is fermented in the reactor with the formation of combustible gas - biogas, which is used for technological and domestic needs. About 1 mt of manure with 90% humidity can produce about 220 m³ of biogas with a calorific value of 28 ... 35 MJ/m³. The remains of the fermentation mass in the digesters are a highly digestible liquid highly concentrated organic fertilizer (humus) easily digestible by plants and devoid of pathogens and weed seeds [8,9].

The main elements of biogas plants are a digester (fermentation reactor) (2) and a gas holder (biogas storage tank) (3). The productivity and economic efficiency of the entire installation depends on the design of the digester.

Biogas plants do not require special expensive equipment. The payback period of these plants is 2 ... 4 years.

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of a biogas plant for individual solar heating at Muborakneftgaz LLC: 1-organic waste; 2-digester; 3-gas holder; 4-solid waste; 5-boiler; 6-engine electric generator; 7-gas stove; 8-heating batteries; 9 and 10-lighting and electrical appliances; 11-heated digester

The main factors determining the widespread adoption in the republic of technology of anaerobic decomposition of organic substances to produce biogas are:

- 1) high technological readiness and economic profitability; technological and operational simplicity of biogas technology;
- 2) for biogas technology, raw materials are available almost everywhere (organic industrial, agricultural and household waste, manure, etc.);
- 3) climatic conditions provide the maximum yield of commercial biogas; winter temperature conditions allow mesophilic fermentation to be ensured (at 30 ... 40 ° C) at minimum biogas costs for heating in digesters, and in the summer time - heating costs disappear;
- 4) wide opportunities for the integrated use of biogas plants in conjunction with solar plants. Biogas usually contains 75 ... 81% methane. Other components include ethane, propane, butane (1,8... 6.2%) [8,9].

The results of the thermophysical characteristics of biogas combustion products obtained from a biogas plant built in a subsidiary farm at Muborakneftgaz LLC are used to

study the heat balances of furnace devices and boiler plants, to simulate heat and mass transfer of heat processes using the heat of fuel combustion products.